

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF JOB SATISFACTION AMONG EMPLOYEES
WORKING IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE HOSPITALS OF
LAHORE**¹Dr Sana Iqbal, ²Mehwish Zulfiqar, ³Haroon Afzaal¹Govt Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot, ²DHQ Gujranwala, ³Lahore Medical and Dental College**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

In hospitals a lot of pharmacists are performing their duties in different ways. Every year a lot of students became pharmacists and performing their duties in different health care centers in Pakistan and also in many other countries. In any job main thing is either person is satisfied with his job or not. If they are not satisfied with their job, they will be mentally upset and will not pay proper attention towards their job. To know this very perform a survey in different pharmacists, that they are satisfied with their job or not. This was taken from those pharmacists who were working in hospitals of Lahore. After this survey we get results where 90% people were satisfied with their job. 10% people was not satisfied with their jobs was due to overloading of work or less experience. That person who was satisfied with their jobs was because of good environmental conditions and handsome salaries. Proper training of pharmacists can improve hospital reputation and employs will also be satisfied.

Keywords: Pharmacists, Lahore hospitals, satisfaction of job.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Sana Iqbal,**

Govt Allama Iqbal Memorial Teaching Hospital Sialkot.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Sana Iqbal et al, *Assessment Of Job Satisfaction Among Employes Working In Public And Private Hospitals Of Lahore.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

Pharmacists play important role in field of science and medicines. In hospitals of Lahore, many pharmacists are working [1]. They have complete knowledge about medicines and use it effectively to treat different diseases and help people [2]. We know pharmacists as benevolent ,care taker, active in his work, more efficient ,loyal, they also have qualities to lead[3].As other countries ,Pakistan is also one of them where 34-36 institutes are available where students get proper degree of pharmacy. Each year 3900 students pass D.Pharmacy and moved towards hospitals for their jobs [4].Hospitals should appoint limited number of candidates/pharmacists to get good quality work. When workers will be satisfied with their job, they will get quality time for work, effective salaries, their o-workers will be o operative then they will do their task more proficiently [5]. Behavior of co workers and effective salaries matter a lot. Promotions and appreciations according to their work mean a lot for workers [6].Person performing their tasks either, it is interesting or tough and person working heartily or not is also an important factor .Another factor that matters a lot is the environment, where employers is working and performing his/her duty, if circumstances will be more favorable, person will be more satisfied with job and will his all tasks with 100% results[7].On the other hand people who show dissatisfaction with their jobs is due to some certain conditions as less promotion chances, high competition level, not increasing salary on

continuous level or any environmental disturbance, atmosphere where they are working is not favorable and relaxing for them[8].

METHODOLOGY:

There was a survey held in three different private and public hospitals of Lahore. These surveys are help in hospital where we find different numbers of pharmacists who work together. We take survey from approximately 65 pharmacists in which 25 were from private hospitals and 35 members was from public hospitals. This survey result was collected in within 15 days. There was multiple type of questions in survey as it was related to age, genders, either person is married or unmarried, they can easily pay their expenses or not, the environment where they are working is comfortable?, staff with which they are performing their duties are friendly or rude., administration with which they are working is fair with them or not, they get their promotions according to their work?. Some questions were related to working environment, salaries, working hours etc. There was different answers according to satisfaction of job, some employers was satisfied with their job and some of them was dissatisfied due to salary issues and some other circumstances.

RESULTS:

With this survey we see different results, if we check findings, some people was satisfied but few of them was dissatisfied with their job.

(Table: 1)

Demographic characteristics	N=	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	24	37.5
Female	40	62.5
Marital status		
Single	30	46.9
Married	34	53.1
Educational qualification		
Pham-D*	24	37.5
Pham-d with Phil	37	57.8
Pham-D with MBA	3	4.7
Workplace facility type		
Public	37	57.8
Private	27	42.2
Unemployment (ever)		
Yes	23	35.9
No	41	64.1
Monthly income PKR		
>30,000	15	23.4
30,000-50,000	35	54.7
<50,000	14	21.9

(Table: 2) Response to job constructs.

In table we check they score of registered pharmacists, either they are satisfied with their jobs or not. Some overall score of those who was satisfied was their job was approximately 86%. And only 34% was those who was dissatisfied due to some issues.

Job constructs	Response N(%)				
	Strongly dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither	Satisfied	Strongly satisfied
Challenging work	12.5	15.6	3.1	57.8	10.9
Monotonous routine of work	10.9	29.7	0.0	53.1	6.3
Skill utilization	7.8	23.4	1.6	59.4	7.8
Work responsibility	10.9	20.3	1.6	54.7	12.5
Work load	6.3	25.0	3.1	56.3	9.4
Amount of prestige	18.8	17.2	1.6	57.8	4.7
Feeling of Accomplishment	14.1	21.9	0.0	54.7	9.4
Job security	10.9	10.9	1.6	60.9	15.6
Salary package	25.0	10.9	1.6	50.0	12.5
Bonuses/rewards/allowances	35.9	9.4	0.0	45.3	9.4
Management capability	7.8	25.0	1.60	50.0	15.6
Fairness of judgement	7.8	25	1.60	53.1	12.5
Effective communication	7.8	18.8	1.60	60.9	10.9
Support and guidance	7.8	29.0	0.0	53.1	17.2
Family time and social life	7.8	31.2	3.1	46.8	10.9
Mental stress and fatigue	7.80	39.1	3.1	46.9	3.1
Shortage of sleep	20.3	31.3	1.60	43.8	3.1
Opportunities for skill enhancement	15.6	29.7	0.0	46.9	7.8
Good working relationship with peers	1.6	14.0	3.10	67.1	14.0
Sufficient place for staff	14.0	32.8	1.6	40.6	10.3
Happiness with administration	6.4	17.1	1.6	59.3	15.6
Enough (casual/sick) leaves throughout the years	12.5	9.3	1.6	54.6	21.8
MS/DMS/DHO concern about staff health	10.9	29.6	1.6	45.3	12.5

(Table: 3) Association between socio demographic characteristics, job constructs and overall job satisfaction.

In this socio demographic table we have checked out their pay scale, age, gender place where they are working, they are facing any health issue or mental stress or not, are their management behaves good with them. Vale of all these points is discussed in this graph.

Variable	P value
Gender	0.693
Marital status	0.312
Educational qualification	2.584
Work place facility type	0.982
Unemployment (ever)	1.21
Monthly income	2.169
Work	0.000*
Pay	0.004*
Management	0.000*
Personal health and well being	0.000*
Working conditions	0.000*

DISCUSSION:

Job satisfaction effects more on hospital reputation, if pharmacists will be satisfy with his salary, colleagues either they are male or female or it these will be friendly environment, when his salary will be good ,he will get promotions[9] .By fulfilling tasks, when worker will be appreciated ,he will do his work in better way, but if his salary will be normal ,colleagues behavior will not be friendly or he will not get promotions[10], he will show dissatisfaction to his job this will effects his work, he will go in mental stress and will not be able to treat patients more effectively. Patients will not satisfy with his performance [11].He will start facing more hardships in his life. These types of surveys are going on in different countries to check response of their employers and by increasing their salaries and by fulfilling their requirements their hospitals will get more publicity either they are public or private hospitals because when they will fill up the requirements of their workers, then employers will give positive response towards administration of hospital and will perform their tasks more happily [12]. In hospitals of Lahore the survey which we held ,we see results like those pharmacists who was registered show positive response toward their job satisfaction but over result for job satisfaction was about 67%.but those who was not satisfied was about 33% [13].Employers who show positive results as registered pharmacists was due to direct contact with the administration. If they face any problem they directly go to their administration and solve issues, as well as guideline from instructors help them to do their tasks in excellent way [14]. They get promotions and their salaries get increase due to their own efforts. They also have good relations with their co workers. We have seen that in graph of pharmacists 47% was satisfied with their job but 37% was dissatisfied, but in registered pharmacists 56% was satisfied because they know that at the end of working they will get good results in way of effective salary and promotions[15]. In any hospital even private hospital, employers will be satisfied with job when they will get good salaries comfortable working conditions[16].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that in hospitals of Lahore we get results as 60% was those registered pharmacists who show satisfaction with their job. But 40% was those who show dissatisfaction. This positive or negative outcomes or due to some issues as mental stress, less payment, or unfavorable environmental conditions.

REFERENCES:

1. Mattsson, S., & Gustafsson, M. (2020). Job Satisfaction among Swedish Pharmacists. *Pharmacy*, 8(3), 127.
2. AlShayban, D. M., Naqvi, A. A., Islam, M. A., Almaskeen, M., Almulla, A., Alali, M., ... & Haseeb, A. (2020). Patient Satisfaction and Their Willingness to Pay for a Pharmacist Counseling Session in Hospital and Community Pharmacies in Saudi Healthcare Settings. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11.
3. Cone, C., & Unni, E. (2020). Achieving consensus using a modified Delphi Technique embedded in Lewin's change management model designed to improve faculty satisfaction in a pharmacy school. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*.
4. Jacobs, S., Hann, M., Bradley, F., Elvey, R., Fegan, T., Halsall, D., ... & Schafheutle, E. I. (2020). Organisational factors associated with safety climate, patient satisfaction and self-reported medicines adherence in community pharmacies. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 16(7), 895-903.
5. Wheeler, J. S., Gray, J. A., Gentry, C. K., & Farr, G. E. (2020). Advancing pharmacy technician training and practice models in the United States: Historical perspectives, workforce development needs, and future opportunities. *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 16(4), 587-590.
6. Bronkhorst, E., Gous, A. G., & Schellack, N. (2020). Practice Guidelines for Clinical Pharmacists in Middle to Low Income Countries. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11.
7. Khairunnisa, P., & Nadjib, M. Effect of Leadership Style on Service Quality and Job Satisfaction among Hospital Nurses: A Systematic Review. In *6th International Conference on Public Health 2019* (pp. 461-470). Sebelas Maret University.
8. Lasebikan, O. A., Ede, O., Lasebikan, N. N., Anyaehie, U. E., Oguzie, G. C., & Chukwujindu, E. D. (2020). Job satisfaction among health professionals in a federal tertiary hospital in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 23(3), 371.
9. Han, J., Kang, H. J., & Kwon, G. H. (2020). Impact of intelligent healthscape quality on nurse job outcomes and job satisfaction: A test of the moderating effect of innovativeness. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 28(1), 43-53.
10. Al-Muallem, N., & Al-Surimi, K. M. (2019). Job satisfaction, work commitment and intention to leave among pharmacists: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ open*, 9(9), e024448.

11. Obeta, U. M., Goyin, L. P., Udenze, C., & Ojo, J. (2019). Assessment of Job Satisfaction Indices among Health Professionals in Jos University Teaching Hospital: An Analytical Study. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 21(2), 38-50.
12. Teong, W. W., Ng, Y. K., Paraidathathu, T., & Chong, W. W. (2019). Job satisfaction and stress levels among community pharmacists in Malaysia. *Journal of Pharmacy Practice and Research*, 49(1), 9-17.
13. Grangeia, R. E., Baptista, R. M., Silva, M. R., Martins, S. P., & Batista, C. F. (2019). IISG-028 An assessment of hospital pharmacists' job satisfaction: application of the job satisfaction survey.
14. AlShayban, D. M., Naqvi, A. A., Islam, M. A., Almaskeen, M., Almulla, A., Alali, M., ... & Haseeb, A. (2020). Patient Satisfaction and Their Willingness to Pay for a Pharmacist Counseling Session in Hospital and Community Pharmacies in Saudi Healthcare Settings. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11.
15. Carvajal, M. J., Popovici, I., & Hardigan, P. C. (2019). Gender and age variations in pharmacists' job satisfaction in the United States. *Pharmacy*, 7(2), 46.
16. Deng, J., Sun, Y., Lei, R., Guo, Y., Liu, J., & Yang, T. (2019). Status of healthcare workers after comprehensive reform of urban public hospitals in Beijing, China: sustainable supply, psychological perception, and work outcomes. *Human resources for health*, 17(1), 77.